

shows a very broad band centered at 18180 cm^{-1} and another at 25000 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transitions of a square-planar nickel(II).

A paramagnetic nickel(II) complexes are representation of a versatile stereoisomerism. The configurational stereochemistry of paramagnetic nickel(II) complexes usually display six-coordinated octahedral, distorted octahedral and five-coordinated trigonal bipyramidal or square-pyramidal or four-coordinated tetrahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$ shows three major bands centered at 10620 , 17000 and 27000 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) transitions, respectively, characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry⁴ of nickel(II) complexes. Various ligand field parameters calculated are as follows : $10Dq$, 10620 cm^{-1} ; B , 809 cm^{-1} ; β , 0.74 ; ν_2/ν_1 , 1.60 .

The magnitude of ligand field parameters ($10Dq$, B) leads to the following conclusions. (i) Ligand Oatsc provides a considerably strong ligand field. If the 'rule of average' is applied and $10Dq$ value of NCS as ligand is taken as 8274 cm^{-1} and value of $10Dq$ comes out to be 11490 cm^{-1} for our novel ligand Oatsc. According to this value, ligand Oatsc may be placed in the spectrochemical series : $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{S}^{2-} < \text{SCN}^- < \text{Cl}^- < \text{NO}_3^- < \text{N}_3^- < \text{F}^- < \text{OH}^- < \text{Urea} < \text{EtOX}^{2-} < \text{OX}^- < \text{H}_2\text{O} < \text{NCS}^- < \text{MeNH}_2 < \text{CH}_3\text{CN}^- < \text{Py} < \text{NH}_3 < \text{en} < \text{NH}_2\text{OH} < \text{SO}_4^{2-} < \text{Oatsc} < \text{Bipy} < o\text{-Phen} < \text{NO}_2^- < \text{Phosph} < \text{CN}^- < \text{CO}$. (ii) The β value suggests strong covalent character of the metal-ligand bond. (iii) The ν_2/ν_1 ratio is 1.60 as expected for octahedral and distorted octahedral nickel(II) complexes.

With a view to obtain pyridine adduct of the square-planar neutral bis-chelate $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$, the complex was dissolved in pyridine. The reddish brown coloured complex completely dissolved to give a reddish orange coloured solution. Depending upon whether one or two pyridine molecules are attached to the planar $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ unit, the species in solution should be expected to be of stereochemical versatility 5-coordinated square-pyramidal or trigonal bipyramidal or six-coordinated octahedral or distorted octahedral. Spectrum of the complex in pyridine solution shows a very strong charge-transfer absorption, tailing deep into the visible region with shoulders at 20000 and 16700 cm^{-1} . A very weak band also lies at 10600 cm^{-1} . The spectrum is however unlike that of an octahedral nickel(II) complex. On removing the solvent by evaporation, the green crystals were formed, which was analysed for $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2(\text{Py})]$. It shows paramagnetism of 3.50 B.M. per nickel atom, corresponding to two unpaired electrons with a large orbital contribution. Electronic spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2(\text{Py})]$ shows bands at 11100 , 15670 , 21050 and 25000

cm^{-1} which suggest for five ligancy trigonal bipyramidal nickel(II) complex.

Infrared spectra : Oximinoacetone-thiosemicarbazone has three coordinating groups, namely, $\text{C}=\text{NOH}$, $\text{C}=\text{S}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ of azomethane group. The oxime group of Oatsc is active only in alkaline medium. Only two of the complexes, viz. $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2(\text{Py})]$, therefore, involve oxime coordination. Earlier literature⁵ have shown that when thiosemicarbazone coordinates through S only the characteristic ($\nu_{\text{CN}} + \delta_{\text{NH}_2}$) band shows a positive shift of $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the case of bidentate coordination through S and N both atoms show a larger shift band of $50\text{--}60\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In free Oatsc ligand the characteristic band is observed at 1585 cm^{-1} and shifts to 1630 cm^{-1} in each complexes of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2\text{X}_2]$ type and hence bidentate coordination is inferred in these complexes. The anions, viz. OAc^- , and SO_4^{2-} show IR bands corresponding to their uncoordinated bonding mode. Only NCS^- in $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ shows bands corresponding to N-coordinated NCS group. According to the above facts a four-coordinated square-planar structure has been proposed for $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2\text{X}_2]$ (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}_2, \text{Br}_2, \text{OAc}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$ and $1/2\text{ SO}_4^{2-}$) and six-coordinate octahedral structure with some distortion involving N-bonded terminal NCS and bidentate Oatsc for $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$.

Infrared spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ is quite different from $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2\text{X}_2]$ type complexes, described earlier. In $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2\text{X}_2]$ type complexes, $\nu_{\text{CN}} + \delta_{\text{NH}_2}$ (which appear at 1585 cm^{-1} in Oatsc) shifts by about 50 cm^{-1} towards higher energy region indicating that hydrazinic N and S both coordinate to Ni^{II} ion.

In $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ complex, the frequency of $\nu_{\text{CN}} + \delta_{\text{NH}_2}$ is observed in the same position (1585 cm^{-1}) suggesting that hydrazinic N of Oatsc does not take part in coordination. The IR ligand band at 3110 cm^{-1} (OH) remains almost unaltered in case of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2\text{X}_2]$ type complexes. In the spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$, this band is considerably perturbed and broadened. The ν_{NO} ligand band (950 cm^{-1}) shifts to higher frequency (1140 cm^{-1}) in the complex. This suggests coordination through nitrogen of the oxime group⁶. The ligand bands at 1060 and 860 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{S}$) are absent in the spectrum of the complex due to thiol formation and coordination through the deprotonated mercaptan group.

On the basis of above discussion it may be concluded that the ligand in $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ coordinates through the deprotonated thiol group as well as the nitrogen of the oxime group. Taking both these groups to coordinate to one metal to form a chelate compound, containing eight-membered ring which is most unlikely and unfavourable. Instead coordination of the two groups with two different metal atom to form

a linear polymeric chain as given below give rise to the most favourable five-membered chelate ring, obtained through hydrogen bonding as shown. Insoluble nature of the complex is in support of such polymeric structure as shown below.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2(\text{Py})]$ shows two bands at 1615 and 1565 cm^{-1} , due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ frequency in the pyridine ring. In pyridine derivatives, two bands at 600–640 cm^{-1} (in-plane ring deformation) are shifted to higher frequency region upon coordination to the ring nitrogen to a metal ion. In the IR spectrum of the present study, the in-plane ring deformation band appears at 720 cm^{-1} , whereas out-of-plane ring deformation band disappears from the spectrum. The $\nu_{\text{CN}} + \delta_{\text{NH}_2}$ band (which is observed at 1585 cm^{-1}) in $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ has apparently merged with the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ of pyridine.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrant. Electronic spectra (nujol) of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu 140 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer and PMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer FT-90 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Synthesis of Oatsc: Oximinoacetone thiosemicarbazone was synthesized involving following steps:

To a solution of thiosemicarbazide (1g) dissolved in hot

water, oximinoacetone (5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring whereupon a white curdy precipitate separated out. It was washed with water, crystallised from ethanol and dried in vacuum at room temperature, m.p. 165°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3320 (NH), 3110 (OH of $\text{HC}=\text{NO}\cdots\text{H}$), 1585 (CN), 1500 (CN+NH), 1450, 1420 (δ_{NH} , ν_{CN} , δ_{NH_2}), 1285, 1250 (δ_{NH} , ν_{CH} , ν_{NH_2} , ν_{CS}), 1090, 1060, 1010 (CS), 950 (NO of $\text{HC}=\text{NO}-\text{H}$), 860 (CS), 780 (NH_2), 570 (δ_{NH}), 520, 480 cm^{-1} (ν_{NCN} , ν_{CS} , δ_{CS}); λ_{max} (EtOH) 230 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 266 nm ($\text{C}=\text{S}$); δ 1.95–2.05 (CH_3), 4.8 (OH of $\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{OH}$), 6.4 ($\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{N}$), 8.65 (m, NH_2 and NH). The compound gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Synthesis of nickel(II) complexes:

$[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc})_2(\text{X}_2)]$ (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}$ and $1/2 \text{SO}_4$): An aqueous solution of Ni^{II} -salt was added dropwise to the ligand using ethanol as reaction medium in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed for ~0.5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with 50% aqueous ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2(\text{Py})]$: Oximinoacetone thiosemicarbazone (Oatsc) was dissolved in hot water. Hydrated nickel sulfate (0.6 g) dissolved in water was made ammonical with a large excess of ammonia to obtain dark blue solution and to it aqueous solution of ligand Oatsc was added. The resulting red coloured precipitate was washed and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, $[\text{Ni}(\text{Oatsc-H})_2]$ prepared as above was dissolved in pyridine. The solution was allowed to evaporate at room temperature. The resulting dark green coloured crystals were washed with 50% ethanol and dried under reduced pressure, yield 35–45%, decomp. temp. 250°.

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